

AN IMPROVED METHOD OF NON-TENSION HERNIOALLOPLASTY FOR INGUINAL HERNIAS

Khujamov Olimjon Bakhridinovich

Atoyeva Mokhigul Otabekovna

Usmonov Amirbek Usmonovich

Arziyev Asilbek Ismoilovich

Saymurodova Shaxnoza Ziyodullayevna

Bukhara State Medical Institute, Republic of Uzbekistan, Bukhara

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Introduction. Lichtenstein's "non-tensioned" technique of inguinal hernioalloplasty has shown a number of obvious advantages over traditional types of inguinal hernia repairs. The operation takes a little time, is easy to perform and is quite acceptable in terms of cost [6]. However, often the inguinal ligament is so loose that it can hardly be a reliable place for fixation of the prosthesis. There is a need for additional fixation. The use of the Cooper ligament for this purpose, as recommended by many authors, only partially solves the problem, while the Kozlov techniques with the formation of an artificial inguinal ligament and Fletching with the use of a "three-layer mesh" are technically complicated [2, 5, 8]. In addition, it is not always possible to observe the "tension-free" principle with the Lichtenstein technique. The encountered weakness of the inguinal ligament makes us resort to grasping a part of the aponeurosis of the external oblique abdominal muscle in a continuous suture for a stronger fixation of the prosthesis. In addition, capturing the Cooper ligament into the suture displaces the inguinal ligament downwards. As a result, suturing of the flaps of the aponeurosis of the external oblique abdominal muscle is impossible without tension. Even slight tissue edema occurring in the postoperative period leads to even greater tension of the anterior wall of the inguinal canal [1, 4]. In general, the described changes show that after implantation of a synthetic prosthesis according to the Lichtenstein method in the tissues of the inguinal region, there are processes that predispose to the development of possible hernia recurrence.

The purpose of the study is to optimize non-tension hernioplasty for inguinal hernias by introducing a new method of alloplasty.

Materials and methods of research. The study is based on the results of examination and treatment of patients with inguinal hernias operated in the surgical department of the multidisciplinary regional hospital of Bukhara in the period from 2018 to 2023. Eighty-five inguinal hernia patients were selected for prospective dynamic active study. They were male patients with different types

of inguinal hernias. The patients were operated both in planned and emergency procedures, and depending on the choice of treatment tactics the patients were divided into two groups. The first group, the comparison group, consisted of 24 (28.2%) patients with inguinal hernias who underwent hernioalloplasty according to the Lichtenstein method. The second, the main group consisted of 61 (71,8%) patients who underwent inguinal hernioalloplasty according to our modified method. The results of surgical treatment of 24 patients of the comparison group who were operated according to the I.L.Lichtenstein method were analyzed. In the early postoperative period seroma of the postoperative wound occurred in 4 (16.7%) patients, which was eliminated by puncture method. Acute urinary retention was observed in 1 (4.2%) patient. 9 (37,5%) of the patients operated according to the I.L.Lichtenstein method at the moment of discharge indicated the feeling of a foreign body in the inguinal region, of which inguinal neuralgia occurred in 3 (33,3%) patients. In 12 months after the operation we managed to examine 23 (93,5%) (out of 24 patients in the comparison group) operated patients, in 1 (4,3%) man after I.L.Lichtenstein method surgery of elderly with benign prostatic hyperplasia, operated for hernia with defect of 3 size and inguinal space more than 3 cm, recurrence of hernia was revealed. Taking into account all the above-mentioned disadvantages and possible complications in the postoperative period, we have developed and introduced into practice a modified inguinal hernioalloplasty.

Results of the study. Reducing the traumatic nature of surgical access with early activation of the operated patients, the possibility of strengthening the posterior wall of the inguinal canal with polypropylene mesh with preperitoneal fixation contributed to a twofold reduction in the duration of postoperative fever, i.e. seroma isolation decreased from 16.7% to 1.6%. After alloplasty, changes in the inguinal canal were studied by ultrasound. In the process of the study, in order to study the constituent tissues of the inguinal canal, the thickness of the rectus abdominis, internal oblique and transverse abdominal muscles, the height of the inguinal space at rest and under tension (leg elevation at 15°) were measured in patients who underwent alloplasty of the hernia defect 1 month after surgery in 47 (77.0%) and 19 (79.2%) patients of the main group and in the comparison group, respectively. After alloplasty (in 1 month) during ultrasonography of the inguinal area the mesh implant behind the seminal canal is well traced regardless of whether the plastic surgery was performed according to the I.L.Lichtenstein technique or preperitoneal alloplasty in the modification proposed by us. The transverse fascia cannot

always be visualized. Under tension, regardless of the type of alloplasty, there was a significant ($p>0.05$) increase in the thickness of the rectus abdominis muscle, internal oblique and transverse abdominal muscles, and the thickness of the inguinal canal. The height of the inguinal space slightly decreased ($p>0.05$). This indicates that the changes in the inguinal region in patients after alloplasty (according to I.L.Lichtenstein technique or preperitoneal hernia defect alloplasty in the proposed modification) at rest and during loading are identical. Thus, during straining the thickness of the inguinal canal reliably increases, and this indicates that the mentioned operations do not disturb the comfortable mechanism of the inguinal canal for the spermatic cord, which prevents a possible disturbance of blood flow in the spermatic cord and testis.

Conclusions: The operation according to the I.L. Lichtenstein method. Lichtenstein operation is technically simple and accessible in performance, but gives hernia recurrence in 5.3% of patients. Preperitoneal alloplasty of the hernia defect in our proposed modification is a reliable alternative to the operation according to the I.L.Lichtenstein method in the treatment of patients with medium and large inguinal hernia, recurrent inguinal hernia, which, if performed correctly, does not give recurrences and has a low number of complications characteristic for alloplasty, which do not depend on the type of the applied mesh implant.

References:

1. Azamat S., Salim D. Factors influencing the choice of hernia repair method in patients with incisional hernias //European science review. – 2017. – №. 1-2. – С. 153-155.
2. Davlatov S. S. et al. Modern Approaches to The Treatment of Patients with Ventral Hernias and Simultaneous Pathologies //International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research (09752366). – 2020. – Т. 12. – №. 3.
3. Davlatov S. S., Mardanov B. A. Верификация системного подхода выполнения симультанных операций на органах брюшной полости и брюшной стенке у больных с вентральной грыжей //Шпитальна хірургія. Журнал імені ЛЯ Ковальчука. – №. 3. – С. 11-16.
4. Kurbaniyazov Z. B. et al. Удосконалений метод ненатяжної герніоалопластики при пахвинних грижах //Шпитальна хірургія. Журнал імені ЛЯ Ковальчука. – 2017. – №. 1. – С. 71-74.
5. Mukhitdinovich S. A., Sulaymonovich D. S., Yahshiboevich S. Z. Prevention of wound complications in endoprosthetics of the abdominal wall for postoperative ventral hernias // Questions of science and education. – 2017. – №. 10 (11). – С. 163-167.

6. Nazyrova F. G. et al. Age-related structural changes in aponeuroses of the rectus abdominal muscles in patients with postoperative ventral hernias //Клінічна та експериментальна патологія. – 2018. – Т. 17. – №. 3.
7. Sayinaev F. K. et al. Modified method for laparoscopic hernioalloplasty in ventral hernias //British Medical Journal. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 3.
8. Shamsiev A. M., Davlatov S. S., Saydullaev Z. Y. Optimization of treatment of patients with postoperative ventral hernia // Science, technology and education. – 2017. – №. 10. – С. 94-99.

